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Spectral Geographies of Race and Gender: Strange Fruit in Mobile, Alabama

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Abstract

This article is about spectral geographies, gender, and race. Following Jacques Derrida (1994) the spectral displaces and blurs presence and absence. Accordingly, space-time is not neatly distinct. Particularly, John Wylie (2007, 172) writes, "in Derrida's hands, spectrality, the revenant being of ghosts, becomes a *hauntology*, which at the same time displaces and marks place. The spectral is thus the very conjuration and unsettling presence and the past. This article explores these questions, what is the relationship between gender, race, memory, and spectral geographies in Mobile, Alabama? What impact does this relationship have on the fields of gender studies, black studies, and geography?"

Keywords

spectral geographies, sex-gender system, gender performativity, anti-Blackness, space

Southern trees bear strange fruit,
 Blood on the leaves and blood at the root,
 Black bodies swinging in the southern breeze,
 Strange fruit hanging from the poplar trees.

Pastoral scene of the gallant south,
 The bulging eyes and the twisted mouth,
 Scent of magnolias, sweet and fresh,
 Then the sudden smell of burning flesh.

Here is fruit for the crows to pluck,
 For the rain to gather, for the wind to suck,
 For the sun to rot, for the trees to drop,
 Here is a strange and bitter crop.

– *Strange Fruit*, Billie Holiday and Abel Meeropol (1937)

Gender is a complex and multidimensional, analytic category of analysis that is necessary for black studies. The late bell hooks' body of work discussed 19th century racial and gender politics that shaped the ways in which racialized/ing gender between Black women and men was tied to white cisgender heteropatriarchy, including *We Real Cool: Black Men and Masculinity* and her 1999 text, *Talking Back*. Feminist Mary Hawkesworth (2006) asserts that gender has become a central, if not the central, analytical concept in gender studies. By extension, then, gender is a critical analytic for Black quotidian life; considering, intersectionality is the assumptive theoretical framework in this article. Following Hawkesworth's (2006) definition, gender is a category of analysis that provides a mechanism, a language to identify and explain social relations in Western traditions (as well as Third World women's oppressions)—which are predicated on binaries and dualisms including man/female, masculine/feminine/able-bodied/disabled bodies. Furthermore, Donna Haraway (2003) contends that dualisms have been persistent in Western traditions; they have all been systemic to the logics and practices of domination of women, people of color and human geographies. Social domination produces a social other, a minoritarian subject that has undergone social domination in various forms. I am particularly interested in the race-based politics in the U.S. South; a race-based politics that also enscribed race-based legal politics to separate, punish, and strip black men of their humanity and breath. This article brings together the feminist praxis that was gifted by bell hooks, geographic knowledge, and the racialized terror practice of lynching in Mobile, Alabama, the city where I was born.

Gender Studies theorizes about intersectionality and geographic concepts that seek to unpack and respond to Western discursive traditions of oppression. I argue that race is a critical concept of gender that is rooted in geographic landscapes. Together these concepts help us question normative conditions across quotidian life for Black men in Mobile, Alabama; how power is a present absence in identity formations, social relations,

and a reproduction of institutions/structures that reifies¹ the unknowing Other, and the extent of gender's functionality. Through one vignettes, this article explores the co-constitutive nature of gender, place, and race to articulate a more accurate picture of the un/conscious racial perversion, particularly anti-blackness that is engrained our U.S. cultural fabric, which ultimately, shapes the way cities contend with racial and gender difference.

Gender serves as an analytic to unpack its implications for identity formations, social relations, institutional disenfranchisement, oppression, as well as discursive powers that maintain oppressive dualisms (male/female, masculine/feminine, and able-bodied/disabled) and maintain gender as a singular, hegemonic category to organize social life. Specifically, people use 'gender' as the fulcrum in the normalization of identity, socialization through discourse, and institutional power that consistently oppresses people. A norm is not the same as a rule, and it is not the same as a law. A norm, according to Judith Butler (2004, 41), "operates within social practices as the implicit standard of normalization". The norm governs the social intelligibility of action, but it is not the same as the action that it governs. In what follows is a definition of gender, not only as an organizing concept for mainstream society that reproduces dualisms, but an analytic category for the fields of gender studies and geography to deconstruct racism, sexism, and classism that produce dualisms.

The field of women and gender studies views gender as an analytic category to deconstruct dualisms, such as man/female, masculine/feminine, and able-bodied/disabled persons. Scholars such as Sandra Harding (1986) and Joan Scott (1986) have conceptualized gender as an analytic category. Hawkesworth (2006, 12) conceptualizes gender as an analytic category, and as a heuristic device that connects the psyche to social organization, social roles to cultural symbols, normative beliefs to sexed embodiedness, and social divisions of labor to systems of power that privilege men. Thereby, I define gender as a heuristic—mediated by its intersecting vectors of power: race, class, ability, and sexual location—that seeks to denaturalize what dominant society establishes—binaristic norms that are deeply rooted in histories of settler colonialism that are inherent in social relations. Furthermore, the fields of women's and gender studies have demonstrated four complementary models of gender: phenomenological, functionalist, postmodernist, and structuralist.

A phenomenological account of gender comes from Steven G. Smith's *Gender Thinking* (1992) which seeks to "illuminate how gender separates in the life world" (Haweksworth 2006, 154). A functionalist account of gender is "depicted as a cultural construct devised to promote particular social functions" (Haweksworth 2006, 154). A postmodern account of gender comes from Judith Butler who argues that "gender must be understood, not as a noun, nor a set of attributes, but as a "doing" a performative act that constitutes identity that it purports to be" (Haweksworth 2006, 158). This account is conceived with probing what is left out of discursive formations that make the sex/gender system natural. I will return to this account later in this paper to unpack two concepts of

¹ Reification, according to Hawkesworth (2006), is the act of viewing a person as a thing—devoid of consciousness.

gender—gender performativity and the sex/gender system. The final account of gender that is notable in the field is a structural account. A structural analysis of gender comes from R.W. Connell who said, “gender is a social practice that is more than a marking of the human body, it is a weaving of a structure of symbols which exaggerate and distort human potential” (Haweksworth 2006, 163). A structural analysis of gender textures our conception of gender in relation to other vectors of power. A critique to viewing gender as an analytic is that it slips into problematic claims about gender as explanations—a signal or a referent to hegemonic dualisms. Also, the ways in which these four frames are understood do not consider intersectionality. The phrase “intersectionality” was coined by Kimberlé Crenshaw (1989) to analyze the ways in which multiple identities at the individual level of experience (i.e., the micro-level) are interlocking, which reflect the interconnected macro-level structures that produce social inequalities. Arguably, Crenshaw (1989) was inspired by the cultural critic bell hooks who stated in *Feminist Theory: From Margin to Center*, “Class structure in American society has been shaped by the racial politic of white supremacy; it is only by analyzing racism and its function in capitalist society that a thorough understanding of class relationships can emerge”. Writing in 1984, hooks focuses on the ways in which oppressive systems including racism, sexism, and classism presses upon black women in a particular way that conditions their lives that colors their perspective in a way that does not translate into justice for black women; but rather, black women must participate in a matrix of domination complete with violence, struggle, and self-determination.

Crenshaw (1989) says, for feminist theory and antiracist policy discourse to embrace the experiences and concerns of Black women, the entire framework that has been used as the basis for translating “women’s experience” or the “Black experience” into concrete policy demands must be rethought and recast. According to Lisa Bowleg (2012), there are two tenants of intersectionality that are paramount: (1) social categories (i.e., gender, race, sexual identity) are not independent and uni-dimension, but they are multiple and mutually constitutive. Also, Bowleg (2012) contends that structural forces shape social identities as well. Therefore, intersectionality is not limited to the micro-level of daily life, but rather, micro-level inequalities backed by city regulation and racist acts are constituted by cisgender heteropatriarchy.

Spectral Geographies, Race, and Place

His name is Michael Donald. Within pseudo-public consciousness, Donald is remembered as the last, documented lynching in American history. The year was 1981. It was springtime. Donald was randomly selected by the Ku Klux Klan who was angry at the African American community in Mobile, Alabama at the time because an African American named, Josephus Andersonan, was charged with the murder of a white police officer but was not found guilty (John Simkin 2016). This upset the Ku Klux Klan and motivated them to illustrate their bigotry by selecting Donald, a young black cisgender man, to be lynched. On Saturday, March 21, 1981, Donald’s lifeless body was swinging from a tree at what is now 114 Michael Donald Ave—a landscape characterized by violence and tragedy that is sanctified by a historical marker. According to Kenneth E. Foote (1997) sanctification refers to the ritual dedication of an event. In this case, a

violent event. Specifically, Foote (1997, 8) adds depth to the landscape of race and place by contending that, “Sanctification involves the creation of what geographers term a ‘sacred’ place—a site set apart from its surroundings and dedicated to the memory of an event, person, or group....As I employ the term, sanctification always requires the site’s ritual dedication to the memory of an event itself or to a martyr, a hero, or group of victims. In this context, 114 Michael Donald Ave—the name of the street itself is an act of sanctification—the conscious effort of placing a plaque in front of the tree where Donald’s body suspended in the air as what Billie Holiday and Abel Meeropol (1937) call “strange fruit”.

Furthermore, ghostly is the spectral. The spectral is sensed in the unsettling of places occupied by racialized and gendered people. In one estimation, the unsettling is activated through a dialogic performance between the spectral (which is the ghostly) and Black people who experience with place and rooted in gender and racial politics at the time. By dialogic performance I mean the ways in which the discursive is taken up to make memories present, felt, affected/affective, and remembered. According to Tim Edensor (2004), remembered is a process that is social and political. Also, remembering unfolds on three levels. Edensor (2004) writes,

First, remembering space has focused upon the construction of specific memoryscapes. Second, contemporary processes of social remembering have been described as becoming increasingly externalized, staged outside the local through the intensified mediatization and commodification of popular sites, myths, and icons. Third, memory is imprinted upon space through the production of ‘historic’ districts where formerly industrial or commercial buildings are converted into upmarket accommodation, retail space, or office space.

Regarding this quote is the way that memoryscapes² are produced through cultural reifications, racial and gender imaginations, and meaning-making processes that happen between people (with their imaginations and senses) and objects/ghostly manifestations. Remembering the lynching of Donald through re-naming a street after him speaks to the ways in which America’s last, documented lynching is necessary to building a local narrative (with national historic imprints in its national fabric) that the murder happened in the past and will not happen again. Although Black public memories provide a litany of racial and gender harms across Mobile, Alabama including lynching. Yet the feelings that overcome me while standing in front of 114 Michael Donald Avenue is shocking. Perhaps the memoryscape, the unsettling geography, is one that is felt when experienced and illusive when conditioned by racial and gender politics that portrays Black masculinity as queer.

The memoryscape in Mobile, AL has been shaped by historic racial, sexual, and gender politics that are mirrored in popular media. bell hooks’ *Black Looks* reminds us

² Memory is social and spatial. According the *Dictionary of Human Geography*, “an inherently geographical activity; places store and evoke personal and collective memories, memories emerge as bodily experiences of being in and moving through space, and memories shape imaginative geographies and material geographies of home, neighborhood, city, nation, and empire. The memory projects of marginalized groups may bear the traces of trauma, such that the possibilities of memory are altered.

that portraits of Black masculinity are shaped by stereotypes of Black people, and particularly Black men. hooks discusses the homogeneity, flatness, and one-dimensional nature of Black masculinity in the media and quotidian realms by saying,

The portrait of Black masculinity that emerges in this work [*Black Looks*] perpetually constructs Black men as “failures” who are psychologically “fucked up,” dangerous, violent, sex maniacs whose insanity is informed by their inability to fulfill their phallogocentric masculine destiny in a racist context.

Historically, Black men have been perceived and conceived as non-human, hypermasculine, body-objects commodified under a capitalist and patriarchal society. These stereotypes of Black masculinity that were circulated from the Reconstruction, through the Civil Rights Movement, and the present-day have produced an illusionary notion of Blackness and Black men. As a result, racial and gender politics become spatialized in physical places and Black men in places have historically been dominated to murderous ends.

Remembering Michael Donald is a part of building the memoryscape that is Michael Donald Ave which is externalized outside the local through plaquehood politics. What this means is that projecting a plaque onto a site of tragedy and violence is an attempt to bracket the event from the present. Yet the sensorial meets the past through the dialogic performance that makes up the social-object relationship. The memoryscape—Michael Donald Ave—as a racialized and gendered landscape that gets built and understood through remembering goes beyond the act of memorializing this one site, but rather, it is one site in a string of sites in the neighborhood that is publically known as the *historic* Mobile, Alabama. All things considered, the memoryscape of Michael Donald Avenue is an unsettling sensorial geography that telescopes race, gender, time, and space. I visited the Avenue; an eerie overcame my body that sent fear in the form of a chill up my spine that was in no way caused by the humid, southern air. This feeling of being placed back to 1981 Mobile, Alabama only verifies that the spectral is ghostly. This personal event is an example of the telescoping of time and space that is realized through the dialogic performance between place and myself as the social actor/spectator. John Wylie (2001, 180) says,

Place talks places through a spectral event of displacing. There is place if there is dislocation, or sudden uncertainty regarding location in space and time, uncertainty regarding even the reliability of these measurants; in other words, if there is a disturbing irruption of doubt or memory, a confounding of past, present and presence all witnessed by a troubled, stricken figure, a figure haunted by this very process.

Wylie (2001) is suggesting that place becomes known through the act of ghostly spectrality that sankofas to its past. Making every iteration of itself touch upon its past state, producing a memoryscape to be witnessed and internalized by whomever the spectral reaches.

Places become the past through the process of remembering, sensing, and the political process of plaquehood (where events are bracketed). Place is a site where memories are almost already materializing in some derivative of its past. Wylie (2001,

176) writes, “measured by ghosts, and activated within an irreducible and original wandering, these places are the past itself, the ceaseless becoming-past of the present in all its inescapable reverence”. Considering a dialogic performance is inherent in wandering, as I stand at 114 Michael Donald Avenue, the sensory feeling of the strange fruit that is Michael Donald’s body is intently sensed as Saturday evening on March 21, 1981. Here, the spectral is witnessed through the feeling of being haunted by a violent past, in the present. Therefore, the spectral geography and memoryscape of 114 Michael Donald Avenue is materialized through witnessing a feeling that blurs binaristic time and space. According to Wylie (2001), place is a punctum of pasts and presents. Therefore, the specific site, 114 Michael Donald Avenue is the site of a violent and tragic past that respatializes the visitor to Saturday evening on March 21, 1981, as a consequence of witnessing the spectral.

Taking this further, Margaret E. Farrar (2010) deftly contends that memory is not solely the history that we tell ourselves, but rather, it is embodied knowledge of certain past that is felt within the body. Memory is also a pre-political feeling within the body—a being that is suspended between thought and the world. Specifically, Farrar (2010, 724) says, “the important point to be taken from these diverse sources is that the body is not simply a container for perception or a vessel to fill with our recollections but is, instead, the intermediary between thought and world, shaping and shaped by both whenever we remember”. Therefore, memory and recollection are almost always coloring conceptions, perceptions, and, by extension, memoryscapes that get translated into public consciousness at varying intensities of language. For 114 Michael Donald Avenue, and more broadly, the Avenue, the haunted is the punctum of testimony—the act of presence. For example, Michael Donald Avenue is an unsettling geography that becomes *unsettled* through the blurring of space and time (read: telescoping time and space). This within itself materializes the spectral. Following this line of thinking, the spectral—perhaps the strange fruit and a ghostly register of violence between two life times—disturbs unsettled geographies and subjectivities as a reminder of the past, which resultably impacts how we might conceive of the present and, possibly, the future.

This article is written with the spectral, not necessarily about the spectral; also the spectral is racialized and gendered, simultaneously. I have allowed the spectral that is tethered to the unsettled geography of Michael Donald Avenue to color my memory to the extent that I can package its effects into words alone.

Although this article is written in sensible registers, what I have attempted to show is that the spectral is located in the interstitial spaces within unsettled geographies. In this sense, the spectral materializes through its ability to affect and become affected by. Two things should be noted here: (1) places are almost already becoming more than what we can sense and (2) places are in and of itself a medium to experience an act from the past as they are punctums of pasts and presents. This is to say that the spectral unsettles a place that is social attempted to be flattened through the act of sanctification. Yet strange fruit never dies. Michael Donald lives on in the memories that are embedded within the unsettled geography that is now Michael Donald Avenue. The *unsettled* of unsettled geography sheds lights on the idea that geographies are always becoming, changing with the spectral and actors’ interpretations of it. Bennie Hays, the second-highest ranking

official in the Klan in Alabama said prior to kidnapping Michael Donald, “If a black man can get away with killing a white man, we ought to be able to get away with killing a black man” (Simkin 2016). Yet they did not, the violence and tragedy that occurred on Michael Donald Ave will forever be known through the witnessing of the spectral that characterizes the Avenue.

Intersectionality illuminates how Black men do not live single-axis lives, but instead oppressions and privileges are almost always interlocking and variably multiplied. As Vivian May (2015) demonstrates, intersectionality discusses power relations that categories of difference create, and white supremacy reifies. Therefore, intersectionality adds depth and texture to the way networks of power further subjugates bodies. Intersectionality peels back the façade that is cisgender white heteropatriarchy so that we, as social actors, understand how we are impacted, directly, in a social system. To be clear, I break away from white feminisms essentialist overtones about “women” and “men” and “Black men” because gender is always mediated by race, class, ethnicity, sexual orientation, nationality, and a host of other vectors of power. Vivian C. Adair (2001) highlights my definition and understanding of gender as an intersectional heuristic because she thinks through the limits and possibilities of intersectionality in the context of poverty and how racialized gendered bodies can experience privilege and penalty at the same time. Lisa Bowleg (2012) discusses the ways that Black gay men have been dealing with intersectionality—micro and macro-level inequality. All of this is to say that I view gender as a vector of power that is mediated by markers of identity such as race, class, sexuality, and able-bodiedness. In what follows are the implications for an intersectional analysis of gender on the sex/gender system, gender performativity, and ability. I frame these concepts of gender using intersectionality to signal, rather than deny, interlocking axes of oppression that emerge from structures of heteropatriarchy, settler colonialism, and white supremacy which are spatial structures. Spatially, penalty and privilege are both suspended to regard each concept as a mode to denaturalize, destabilize, and decolonize categories of racialized gender.

Concepts of Gender and Geography

Western conceptions of space consider space an envelope of social relations. Dominant conceptions of public space, for example have been an asylum (Kirstie Bowden 2012), a bar (Elizabeth Armstrong and Suzanne Cragge (2006), and a bathroom (Sheila Cavanagh 2010). Cavanagh (2010), particularly, challenges Western conceptions of space to consider gender and sexuality in its conceptual framework. Cavanagh (2010) theorizes how and why the public bathroom is a space for gender-based hostility, anxiety, fear, and desire; the bathroom is a site of homoerotic desire in addition to social relations. In her theorization, “space is the mechanism by which we negotiate gender identity and social difference” (Cavanagh 2010, 12). Steve Pile argues elsewhere that space is where the body is territorialized and deterritorialized. What this means is that space is where defense mechanisms, internalized authorities, intense feelings, and power and meaning converge (Cavanagh 2010, 11). Considering this, space is an environment also produced by Black LGBT people through action. Black space, then, takes Western conceptions of space and all its dimensions: mental, social, and physical (Lefebvre 1991) further. Black

space is a concept that assumes that Black geographies and people exist and attends to their navigation of anti-Black racism. In addition, Black space also attends to gender politics that are sited in a particular geographic context, such as in Mobile.

Gender functions as an object of analysis for social relations. The function of gender constitutes the evolution of the field of women's and gender studies. Defining gender is a task of conceptualizing and understanding *gender* that requires a consideration of gender in material, discursive, and biologic contexts. In the discursive sense, gender is a regulatory norm, but it is also one that is produced in the service of other kinds of regulation (Butler 2004). By regulation, I mean the ways that language and actions, as two examples, are policed by way of other people, laws, and/or policies. Moreover, regulation stems from the network of power. Power in this sense means that it is diffused, rather than top-down, unidirectional. Also, gender is a vector of power that serves an organizing principle for social life with material consequences. In the case of Michael Donald, then, gender and racial politics under white cisgender heteropatriarchy creates a host of material consequences that cost young Black men and boys a livable life.

At the turn of the century, Black feminists incorporated social constructionism into their conception of gender which riddled the sex/gender system's epistemological center. Elsa Barkley Brown (1992) reminds us that gender does not have a voice, but people do. In the case of Michael Donald, white male masculinity and performance actively oppresses and threatens to ensure its legitimation in the Western frame. Social constructionism, might I add, proposed positive insight for the field of women and gender studies. According to Butler (2004, 1), "gender is a kind of doing, an incessant activity performed, in part, without one's knowing and without one's willing, it is not for that reason automatic or mechanical". Therefore, gender is performed and performative such that hegemonic notions of gender are damaging to Black people, literally. Hegemonic notions of gender are predicated on the sex/gender system. The sex/gender system challenges and informs feminist research because it is used to foreground a critical understanding of oppressive structures which are rooted in settler colonialism. Jennifer Nez Denetdale (2009) centers the sex/gender system to serve as a mechanism through which nationalism, militarism, and patriotism is read and understood. The sex/gender system, as Denetdale (2009) uses the concept, is one that takes up feminist analysis for research to "shed light on how patriarchy operates as the structural system of domination, which diffuses questions of discrimination across race and other differences while bifurcating gender as feminine and masculine" (Denetdale 2009, 135). The sex/gender system, as a concept, was integral to the challenge of Anne Fausto-Sterling (2005). Fausto-Sterling (2005) argues that sex-gender system accounts of difference fail to appreciate the degree to which culture is complicit in producing body systems referred to as biology—something apart from the social. Therefore, from the 1970s to the turn of the 21st century the sex/gender system, as a concept of gender, is used to trace when, how, and the effects of understanding that gender/sex are interchangeable in the human domain. This has implications on feminist spatial research because it expands the horizon of gender to placemaking. The sex/gender system provides a critical perspective of gender. In a social constructivist sense, gender is a socio-cultural production that manages sex categories and ascribes meanings to those categories. For example, dominant society

ascribes “masculine” and “feminine” to sexed bodies. Yet a feminist approach to the sex/gender system draws distinctions between sex and gender categories; however, the sex/gender distinction is a critique to the hegemonic notion that sex and gender are the same. Butler (2004, 10) reminds us, “masculine” and “feminine” are notoriously changeable; there are social histories for each term; their meanings change radically depending upon geopolitical boundaries and cultural constraints on who is imagining whom, and for what purpose”.

In addition, *gender performativity* is a concept of gender that functions as a mechanism by which notions of masculine and feminine are produced and naturalized through performance and spatial power. By spatial power, I mean the ways in which people struggle over space and that struggle ends in threats and/or death. I define gender performativity as the active resistance of normative gender norms using bodily acts which are mediated through symbols/meanings; it uses embodied knowledges to extend performativity and create alternate options of gender by doing so. Notably, gender performativity has been identified for its discursive power to deconstruct gender essentialism and biological determinism. In terms of performance and social relations, I rely on feminist scholarship of Judith Butler (2004) who argues that gender is the apparatus by which such terms such as masculine and feminine are deconstructed and denaturalized (2004, 42). Thus, this means that gender is socially constituted and mis/recognized by way of performance and social formations, the relationship of *recognizable* binaristic gestures (read: performances) of masculinity and femininity, alongside its material iterations of its bodily attachments and corporeal performance, focused primarily on the way that Black men perform masculinity that threatens white male masculinity. These turns also shaped and is shaping, the way we challenge and inform feminist research. Therefore, in the context of social constructionism, gender challenges notions that render it static, which means that that seem to attempt to pin down or concretize gender as a form of social power that produces the intelligible field of subjects, and an apparatus by which the gender binary is constituted (Butler 2004).

Furthermore, Aida Hurtado (1997) discusses the inherent masculinism and sexism in the State that further marginalizes women and people of color. Hurtado (1997) traces such claims back to the critical social theory of Marx and Ramalagzou to make the point that gender is performed and understood as a force of power and domination. This means that codes of protection are largely based on gender performativity, which follows a rubric to regulate racially gendered bodies and serves as a precursor to vulnerability and degradation. To be clear, protection of the State is gendered and assumes a white subject. This assumption is contextualized in Cheryl Harris’ (1993) notion that whiteness is seen as valuable property and the State protects this property and reproduces the white subject as the norm. Thus, any disidentification from this norm is rendered deviant which makes gender performativity—the means by which racialized bodies must perform the script of white hegemonic masculinity while also navigating the racial politics in Mobile, Alabama (Lisa Bowleg 2012). In terms of material critique of gender performativity, Dean Spade (2010) says that material matters while pushing back on an essential body. Spade (2010) wants to tease apart the implications of medicalized gender norms on medical procedures. To do this, Spade (2010) focuses on negation of medical knowledge in trans* person’s

personal and legal struggles. Particularly, Spade (2010) unpacks the ways in which medical evidence is entrenched when seeking to expand trans* rights. Spade (2010, 18), writes, “sex-reassignment related procedures are regulated through a mental health model which promotes regulatory, binary gender expression and denies access to medical procedures to those who fail to perform normative binary gender for their health care providers. Elizabeth Wilson (2015) calls attention to the putative antibiologism in feminist theory to contest our taken for granted understandings of mind and body. Wilson (2015) offers a biological critique for biology in feminism that biological data aids feminist theory in ways. In her words, biological data is “helpful” which means that it is” arresting, transforming, and taxing” (Wilson 2015, 2). In her conceptual, political and methodological intervention in reaction to the displacement of biology in feminism, Wilson (2015) claims that the goal of gut feminism—which connects biological data and feminism—is to think through the implications the interconnectedness of the gut (which accumulates bile) and the mind. Using Gayle Rubin (1999), Sigmund Freud’s theories of hysteria and melancholy, Judith Butler’s (1997) essay on gender melancholy, and contingency, Wilson (2015) introduces gut feminism as a method to read biology and harm and as a theory that “is able to think innovatively and organically at the same time” Wilson (2015, 17). This is relevant as it demonstrates the ways in which Wilson’s (2015) gut feminism approaches the conceptualization of gender in a way that is not a “flat, sovereign substrate”. Rather, Wilson (2015) is interested in biological events that show evidence of a biological unconscious— “a biology that could be in a forlorn and destructive relation to itself and the world” (70). The primary reason here is that gut feminism goes beyond flat ontologies to offer material critiques of gender performativity that demonstrates the intra-action between the gut and brain, drugs and discourse, biology, and culture. I argue that gender performativity and performativity are racialized performances that are linked to racial politics, particularly in Mobile, Alabama. The white male masculinity demands control of Black men’s bodies like the ways in which white men during chattel slavery controlled the Black male body. Michael Donald’s lynching, then, is a fatal example that white male masculinity systematizes placemaking and anti-Black racism that calls attention to the influence of place.

The politics of place and placemaking informs feminist research on gender performativity and racial politics. The epistemological and spatial turns in scholarship on gender has been informed by race and gender. These turns have opened avenues for feminist research, methodologies, and theories about memory, spectral geographies, and gender performativity. The material consequences, while varied, are mapped using a historical focus on anti-Black racism against Black masculine presenting people. For example, Marlon M. Bailey (2013) discusses racialized gender performativity as an important aspect that demonstrates an intersectional approach to gender performativity. According to Bailey (2013), because a matrix of identities exists, there is a need to reconfigure gender as a vector of power that is mediated. More specifically, Bailey takes up gender performance as means to “make it possible to revise, negotiate, and reconstitute gender and sexual categories and norms” (Bailey 2013, 18). As another example of racialized gender performativity, Martin F. Manalansan (2003) provides another notable example of racialized gender performativity by centering Filipino gay men’s negotiations

between bakla and gay traditions in New York City. Manalansan (2003)'s intervention is interested in aligning racialized gender performativity and intersections of race, class, sexuality, and gender outside normative notions to expand taken for granted notions of cultural citizenship—the sense of belonging and personhood. Taken together, both gender scholars' theorizations are rooted in spatial knowledge and literal places; the sex/gender system, gender performativity, and performance are realms of feminist scholarship that is almost already geographic.

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